

About UP-TO-ME

The UP-TO-ME Concept

The UP-TO-ME technology will capture and utilise the CO₂ for methanol production and simultaneously upgrade the biogas to biomethane.

As a first byproduct, biomethane can be used as a substitute for natural gas and as a fuel for heavy goods vehicles, allowing biomethane injection into the existing natural gas grid.

The fully automated, self-learning and self-optimising control system allows the production of methanol under fluctuating conditions. This can be achieved by combining dynamic plant models and artificial intelligence to provide self-optimising control of off-grid operations, which is very challenging and has never been done before.

The ability of a remote plant to adapt itself to varying boundary conditions such as the availability of renewable energies, or the availability of CO₂ from a fluctuating source will open a variety of possibilities for distribution production.

UP-TO-ME

Unmanned Power-to-Methanol-production

UP-TO-ME is an EU funded project that targets a ground-breaking change in decentralised Power-to-Methanol -production for hard to electrify applications, like marine vessels.

Our Project Partners

Get in touch to find out more about our ground-breaking project

✉ info@up-to-me.com

🌐 up-to-me.com

🐦 [@horizontoptome](https://twitter.com/horizontoptome)

🌐 [Horizon UP-TO-ME](https://www.linkedin.com/company/horizon-up-to-me/)

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This project is taking on the great challenge of converting decentralised CO₂ point-sources to production sites for renewable fuels with the aim of significantly impacting the global journey to a net-zero EU economy.

See inside to find out more

The Maritime Industry

Why we need UP-TO-ME

Globally, over 90% of traded goods is transported by sea, these marine fuels release around 2,600 times more sulphur than road fuel. Sulphur in fuel releases Sulphur Dioxide into the atmosphere causing high air pollution and other environmental risks.

This is just one reason the UP-TO-ME project aims to create a completely renewable biofuel suitable for marine vessels. Providing a more efficient and environmentally friendly fuel option for marine vessels will ensure our global trading requirements will not be interrupted.

The UP-TO-ME approach

The outcome of the project is a fully integrated, autonomous (unmanned) Power-to-Methanol plant, which enables the use of CO₂ from biogenic point sources and locally available renewable energy.

The biogas produced in the anaerobic digestion of sewage sludge contains on average 65% methane and 35% CO₂. Our technology will capture and utilise the CO₂ for methanol production and simultaneously upgrade the biogas to biomethane.

The smart self-optimising dynamic operation enables the reduction of intermediates storage such as H₂. The process also allows upgrading of biogas and biomethane for further distribution and thus, enabling wider use of biogas plants as carbon-neutral sources for fuels, and chemicals for transportation and industry.

UP-TO-ME objectives

UP-TO-ME will produce at least 100 litres of concentrated methanol (approx. 95 mass-% of methanol) in the experimental plant. The patented process to be implemented reduces energy requirements by 30% compared to conventional mine-based technology.

